

Sample Name: PA UV 5-10 μm

Material: Polyamide (Nylon-6,6)

Size: 5-10 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Structure

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50_v}) = 9,55 μm
- Particles have a rounded, irregular morphology
- $7,0 \times 10^{10}$ particles per gram
- 6612 cm^2/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$ (PA) determined by XRF
- No changes due to milling or aging observed in FTIR spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PA spectrum

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50_v} : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50_N} : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using *Static Light Scattering (SLS)* provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
12,30	7,96	3,13	0,95	0,57	9,55	$7,0 \times 10^{10}$	6612

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$	99,937
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	74
S	11
Cl	2040
K	19
Ca	29
Ti	2
Cr	23
Mn	1
Fe	86
Ni	7
Cu	2
Zn	2
Mo	1

Chemical Bonding (Using $\mu\text{-FTIR}$ provided by TNO)

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (provided by TNO)

